

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

NTN3 (netrin 3)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	4917 / O00634
Target Nominator	TREAT-AD
TREAT-AD Authors	Emory-Sage-SGC-JAX TREAT-AD Center
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TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target is found within a TMT proteomics network module that was highly correlated with cognition. This module (Module 42) contains several novel AD targets, including SMOC1 and SFRP1.

TREAT-AD Target Risk Score: 3.93 (rank #494, 98th percentile)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's Disease, and is the sum of the target's Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

For more information or questions regarding the TEP, please contact treatad.info@sagebionetworks.org

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for this target is 2.54 out of 5 (rank #7746, 69th percentile). The individual score components include 0.57 of 3 for genetics, and 1.97 out of 2 for genomics. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of NTN3, both protein and RNA, is significantly increased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. NTN3 is annotated to GO terms from the Synapse and Proteostasis domains.

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Seattle Alzheimer's Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD). The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins. The expression of the target in subtypes within each broad class is shown as a point. Blue points show the summary expression of cells from individuals with no dementia, while red points show summary metrics of cells from dementia patients. Open circles reflect low confidence measures of expression.

The expression of NTN3 is not confidently detected in any cells within this dataset.

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

NTN3 (netrin-3) and family member NTN1 were both identified in our large scale proteomic studies of differential expression in postmortem AD brains as part of a module linked to AD pathology and clinical cognitive decline (1). Here we report on the development of a basic target enablement package (TEP) for NTN3 consisting of purified protein, antibodies validated in knockout cell lines for NTN3 specificity and dual functionality in both biochemical and immunohistochemical studies, and a full bioinformatic characterization. The role of NTN3 in AD is unknown and warrants further investigation, based on the biology discussed below, and we hope the resources generated by TREAT-AD in this NTN3 TEP will decrease the barrier to future investigations of the biological role of NTN3 in AD.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

NTN3 (netrin-3) is a 580 amino acid protein expressed throughout the cerebral cortex that is involved in axon projection regulation in neurodevelopment(2, 3). The protein is observed within the Golgi and in the extracellular space, consistent with its passage through the secretory pathway, its glycolytic maturation, and its role in regulating axon guidance. NTN3 shares 3 laminin EGF-like domains with other members of the netrin family (Prosite: O00634) and it is believed to signal in similar fashion to NTN1, namely, through an association with the netrin receptors DCC and UNC5(2, 4). The downstream signalling of the netrins 1-3 modulates axonal projection termination, and specifically functions in axon repulsion(5). Consistently, NTN3 dysregulation in sensory neurons is linked with diabetic neuropathic pain (DNC), in which decreased levels of NTN3 are associated with aberrant sensory neuron projections into the epidermis, and conversely, increased NTN3 expression decreased sensory neuronal projection into the epidermal area and decreased levels of DNC in transgenic diabetic mice(5). Interestingly, NTN3 is also associated with involved in neuroblastoma progression, in which NTN3 is associated with the aggressiveness and survival of the neuroblastoma(4, 6). The autocrine signalling of NTN3 within neuroblastoma cells, promotes a decrease in migration, and an attachment via focal adhesions(6). Consequently, it appears that NTN3 may function in an analogous manner within both neurodevelopment and oncogenesis to stop the progression of either axon or tumour, promoting local adhesion.

The connection of NTN3 to neurodegeneration or Alzheimer's disease is unclear, but NTN3 does appear in the detergent insoluble fraction as one of 84 differentially expressed proteins in AD brains, based on combinatorial mass spectrometry studies(7). NTN3's role in presynaptic guidance and termination, supports speculation that it may regulate synaptic remodelling and stabilization in mature organisms. Our work identified NTN3 (and paralog NTN1) as core proteins within module 42 (M42), a module that is highly linked with progression of AD pathology and clinical cognitive dementia, within large scale deep proteomic investigations(1). Given the participation of both NTN1 and NTN3 within M42, it seems likely that netrin family function is significant to M42's biological role in AD. APP and APOE are also members of M42 further supporting its association with AD pathogenesis. While the investigation is nascent connecting NTN3 and AD, further exploration is warranted by the scientific community, and the resources described above will hopefully aid in that endeavour.

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further biological investigation of the role of NTN3 in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

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ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

References

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